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वास्तव्य वाटिका
कुरुक्षेत्र

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The First Independence Struggle of India: A Study of Agrarian Aspect

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Abstract

1857 was the first Independence struggle of India. The struggle was born out of historical processes sequence from the British policy conquest and expansion to the colonial exploitation of India. The colonial regime in India started with the annexation of Bengal in the latter half of the 18th century. After the annexation of Bengal till the beginning of the 19th century, The East India Company got established as the supreme power in India. The British adopted the Capitalist economy India and implemented European Feudal System which was based on the exploitation of Indians. The east India Company defined revenue Provision and arrangements differently and different areas according to their own benefits. Accordingly the Zamindari settlement, Ryotwari settlement, Mahalwari settlement and some other revenue arrangements were implemented according to the regional conditions. The purpose of all the arrangement and policy was only to enrich the blaze of the Company.

Key-Words : Mortgage, Possession, Revenue, Landlord, Majority

With the establishment of the British rule, the prevalent revenue system was destined to end. But during this phase of destruction and construction there was to be a vacuum time period in which new methods were to be experimented. Since ancient times land revenue was considered to be the main source of income, so the company tried to make full use of this fact.¹ During this time the three forms of land revenue were prevalent which influenced decisively the production, distribution, conversion and utilization in the field of agriculture, this in turn influenced the socio-economic life in various sector.² As a result everyone related to agricultural faced this destruction be it a peasant, landlord or taluqdars. The British wanted that property rights reforms stimulated land market transactions in 19th century rural India. There was little direct evidence on just how often land ownership rights changed hands.³

The first landmass that was taken under the control by the British was Bengal presidency. It was, however, Cornwallis who made the first significant move for a change in the administration of land in 1793, by introducing the system of Permanent Settlement. The system conferred, for the first time, proprietary rights on the zamindars over the lands they looked after on payment of a fixed amount of land tax to the Government the rightful owner of all lands.⁴ The permanent settlement recognized the landholder's as the proprietors of the soil with the right of hereditary succession for their heirs and lawful successors. They had also the right to transfer, sell or mortgage the land in their possession. But all their rights ceased with their failure to pay

the fixed revenue on the fixed date at the government treasury.⁵ Permanent settlement attached possession to revenue payment. In the past, non payers could be punished in their person by imprisonment. Now their property was at risk. Some great Zamindars lost out as revenue demand was often set at rates that were initially very high.⁶

B.R. Tomlinson has described that many existing Zamindars could not work the new system properly. Economic conditions were disturbed by depression and the aftermath of the great famine of 1769-70; the effective power of many Zamindars to extract rent from their tenants and to control their officials was often small. Between 1794 to 1807 the lands on which 41 percent of the governments revenue depended changed hands at fairly low prices, although within twenty years or so a stable landed interest had been established, and the 'rule of property' created in Bengal.⁷ The number of estates of defaulting Zamindars, which for want of bidders in the early years of the depressed land market remained with the government, and portion of the immense waste land which at the time of the settlement were not included to cultivation and due to rising prices.⁸

After the long experiments in the Zamindari settlement and village lease between 1813 to 1822, Ryotwari Settlement was reintroduced.⁹ Now this system was called a middle Ryotwari period which lasted up to 1855. During this period, the land revenue was lowered in theory to 50 percent of the gross produce of the wet lands and 33 percent of the dry. Dry land was assessed on the supposition that it yields one crop, if it yields a second dry crop, no extra charge is made.¹⁰ Though Tirthankar Roy is of the opinion that in Ryotwari regions there was increase in land transfer but the main reason behind it was the peasants lost their lands due to their moneylenders and this too could not bring about any change in the agrarian relations.

Dharma Kumar was of the view that the reason of the peasant's indebtedness was not the high rate of rent rather the crop failure, natural calamities and low income of majority of the peasants forced them to take the loan from the moneylenders. This extra burden imposed on the peasants of these regions, in turn forced the self reliant peasants to change into agricultural labourers which included even the artisans of the village. The land rights got centralized to the moneylenders and the landlords. This resulted into very miserable condition of the peasants. The land revenue was collected in cash in the non-irrigated area where as in the irrigated areas the government would collect a certain amount of the produce in place of the land revenue. Even then the government had an inclination to collect the land revenue in cash.¹¹ Sir George Clark said in front of the British Parliament Committee that in the Ryotwari regions the condition of the peasants was like beggars.¹²

B.R. Tomlinson opines that the Ryotwari Settlement had declared that the half of the land of Bombay (South Dakkan) was barren land in 1838 where as at other places the declining prices, declining trade and economic crisis showed a common decline in the general economic system that destroyed all hope for the development of agriculture with the principle of Ryotwari. Tomlinson supported the view of Eric Stocke and pointed out that during the year 1857 there were mud huts and few utensils to cook and eat.¹³

In 1856, about the merger of Awadh, John William Kay says that the two-third part of Awadh was still under the control of the Talukedars but the British government considered them only the mediators for the collection of the land revenue.¹⁴ Talukedars witnessed great loss due to this policy of the government as they were evicted from their patrimonial land. The majority of these Talukedars had government land in inheritance, as a reward for special service to the state or occupied in illegal ways at the time of the decline of the Mughals. As a result Company ordered to have detailed investigation. Describing this investigation T.R. Holmes believes that

the settlement officers branded the Talukedars as a set of worthless drones, and they decided accordingly to deprive them of the privileges of settling for every foot of land to which they could not show a proprietary title precise enough to satisfy an English lawyer. A few thoughtful men did indeed urge that these sweeping measures would destroy the attachment of the aristocracy to the British rule, and that, if they ever turned against us, we should fine the villagers, whom we had given Bombay area¹⁵. The peasants were left with such a meagre part of the produce that they were neither able to take care of even the basic necessities of their families, nor could pay off their debts and bear the expenses of agriculture. Tomlinson has recorded owns that the British rulers were very well aware of the destructive effects of this new land management. In spite of this fact the British rulers established the Ryotwari Settlement in the whole of India till 1864 to increase the land revenue and its collection. The historians of Cambridge school present the fact about the bad condition of the peasants and the failure of the agriculture policy.¹⁶

Just like the Ryotwari Settlement even the Mahalwari Settlement too was guided by the abolishment of the mediators and was motivated with the idea to maximise the revenue collections of the government by not delimiting the revenue demands permanently. This resulted into the betterment of the peasants and at the same time freed them from the burden of the ever flourishing parasitic group. First from the very onset the revenue was collected very rigidly that led to the selling of land of many landowners.¹⁷ Kay and Melson were of the view that due to our transformed system the owners of large estates were left only with mud houses and utensils for cooking food.¹⁸ The warnings, however, were unheeded, and their authors were ridiculed as alarmists. The mere fact that the settlement aroused discontent did not indeed prove that the principles upon which it was based were false. But perhaps it would have succeeded better if they had reflected that the proprietary right was not the only right connected with the soil, and while taking care to provide valid guarantees for the immunity of the village proprietors from extortion, had recognized the existing rights of the Talukedars for the collection of revenue. While describing this enquiry historian J.W. Kay says that the recovery officer had full authority and the people were instructed to show the papers of their patrimonial rights so that they would be convinced. The people felt that after enjoying the property peacefully for such a long time the demand of papers was irrelevant because the only proof they had was their possession of the land. This led to a terror all around. It won't be wrong to say that all this is called complete possession¹⁹. But as Thomas Metcalf concedes "one can hardly say that nothing happened. The grievances of the rural society of north India were to be expressed rather loudly and violently in the struggle of 1857."²⁰

From this study it is clear that till the middle of the nineteenth century the East India Company created the private property on the land and provided ownership rights to three different groups and produced three types of land settlement i.e. Permanent settlement, Ryotwari settlement and Mahalwari settlement. From the very onset, these settlements were responsible for the backwardness of agriculture and the poverty of peasants. The main aims of the government were being to adopt these three systems was to collect the maximum land revenue. The amount that was levied on the peasants on the form of land revenue was so high that the peasants had to take loan from the moneylenders who exploited the peasants a lot. The peasants were feeling victim to the atrocities not only to the British officers but also the moneylenders. If studied deeply, we find that only no one party was being responsible for the poor position of the peasants like socio economics etc. But the nature, government, moneylender and landlords were responsible. Even the peasant himself was responsible for the same to a great extent. As a loan whatever the peasant would get money from any moneylenders and the landlords then he would

get it by selling his crops and he would commit to spend it on the useless things than on the agricultural works. All these led to the decline in the economic condition of the peasant in the society.

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